

Survey of Ants (Hymenoptera: Formicidae) of Misamis Oriental, Mindanao Island, Philippines

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Abstract

Ant research in the Philippines, particularly in Mindanao, is still in its early stages due to the limited taxonomic expertise and a research focus concentrated primarily in Luzon and Visayas. This study aimed to contribute additional data on ant diversity in Mindanao specifically in Misamis Oriental province. The survey documented 202 ant species representing seven subfamilies and 46 genera. Notable findings include six apparent new Philippine records (*Aenictus itoi* nr, *Parasyscia indica* nr, *Plagiolepis bicolor*, *Polyrhachis danum*, *Tapinoma jandai*, and *Tetramorium validiusculum*) and 17 new distributional records for Mindanao. A substantial portion of the collected specimens (84 species) could not be conclusively identified to the species level, although 18 were assigned near a species and eight suspected new species. These results suggest a rich but poorly understood ant fauna in the Philippines. The high number of unidentified species underscores the critical need for improved species-level taxonomy, including identification keys and reference materials to facilitate accurate species identification and further our understanding of Philippine ant biodiversity.

Key words: Biodiversity, new records, species identification, Southeast Asia, taxonomy

Introduction

The Philippines is a tropical country that is archipelagic in nature with more than 7,600 islands, having mountainous terrains, dense forests, plains, and coastal areas. With this, despite the country's relatively small size, it is considered as one of the world's most biologically rich countries (Layos et al., 2022). Tropical countries are considered as the hotspot for ant diversity due to high temperature and high precipitation (Dantas & Fonesca, 2023). Kass et al., (2022) also added that many under sampled Philippine and Indonesian islands likely contain hidden rare ant hotspots, making this a globally important region for ant biodiversity.

Ants offer a lot of ecosystem and other services such as pharmaceuticals and medicines, food, pollination, biological control and indicator data, seed dispersal, bioturbation, nutrient cycling and decomposition, carbon cycling, energy flow, literature and arts, and cultural traditions and religion (Elizalde et al., 2020). However, ant faunas are incompletely explored and information concerning them is widely scattered (General & Alpert, 2012). Currently, there are only 229 ant species recorded from Mindanao (General et al., 2024; antwiki.org), out of 570 species across the entire Philippines (antweb.org), with more than 100 undescribed species. These statistics are based on publicly available database resources, and do not include specimens in collections that have not been database.

With the rise of biodiversity surveys in the Philippines, Mindanao offers many locations whose exploration will improve our understanding of ant biogeography. Only three systematic transect surveys have been conducted: in the World Heritage Site of Mt. Hamiguitan in Davao Oriental (General & Buenavente, 2017), Mt. Bungkasan in Bukidnon Province (General, 2021), and Mt. Melibengoy in South

Cotabato (General et al., 2024). In their study, General and Buenavente (2017) discovered 122 species from 55 genera, including 14 new Philippine records; General (2021) found 75 species across 39 genera, with nine new Philippine records; and General et al. (2024) documented 87 species from 33 genera, with three new Philippine records.

Mindanao remains an underexplored island in terms of ant study, General (2021) attributes ant diversity challenges in the region to: complex geography causing vicariance and dispersal, coarse species distribution resolution due to island variability, and limited research/funding. Another factor is the safety and security of the researchers since some mountains of Mindanao are in active conflict zones, such as those in Bukidnon and, in this study, Misamis Oriental. Additionally, socioeconomic and political problems hinder studies and conservation in the country (Layos et al., 2022). With more research, especially in less-studied areas, the total of known ant species is likely to increase (Kass et al., 2022). The current contribution adds knowledge of both Mindanao's ant fauna and the Philippine ant fauna in general.

Materials and methods

The study was conducted in selected areas of Misamis Oriental, namely: Mimbilisan Protected Landscape, Sumagaya-Lumot Range and Mt. Balatukan Range Natural Park. The sampling was conducted between October 2021 and April 2024.

Misamis Oriental is a province located in the northern part of Mindanao, Philippines. It shares land borders with Lanao del Norte and Bukidnon provinces to the south, Agusan province to the east, and its northern coast faces the Bohol Sea. Mimbilisan Protected Landscape is a lowland riparian forest with an elevation of about 450-480masl. Sumagaya-Lumot Range is a mixed secondary dipterocarp forest with an elevation of about 1000-1200masl. Mt. Balatukan Range Natural Park is a mixed dipterocarp forest with an elevation of about 1400-2000masl.

Figure 1 depicts the geographic distribution of ant surveys across Mindanao Island, Philippines. The map uses various markers to indicate the approximate locations of different studies: purple triangles for opportunistic sampling in Misamis Oriental (this contribution), a red dot for opportunistic sampling near Lake Holon (Mt. Melibengoy, South Cotabato) (General et al., 2024), a yellow dot for a transect study on the Pantaron Range (Bukidnon) (General, 2021), and a blue dot for a transect study on Mt. Hamiguitan (Davao Oriental) (General & Buenavente, 2017).

Figure 1. Location of the study sites in the Philippines (left), Mindanao (right), and the sampling area of Misamis Oriental (inset). Map created by April Rose Monding using QGIS-LTR version 3.40.4-Bratislava. Triangles represent current study sites; the significance of other map markers is explained in text.

The collection method for the specimens was mainly opportunistic hand collecting for larger specimens and the use of a watercolor brush for smaller specimens. The collected samples were then preserved with 95% EtOH in 5ml vials.

Dry mounted representative samples on teardrop-shaped cards were initially identified at the genus level using published keys (General & Alpert, 2012; General, 2024). Subsequently, species identification was carried out using various genus-specific keys: *Acanthomyrmex* (Moffett, 1986); *Anochetus* (Zettel, 2012); *Aenictus* (Jaitrong & Yamane, 2011, 2013); *Camponotus* part (Dhadwal & Bharti, 2023); *Carebara* part (Liu et al., 2024); *Cataulacus* (Bolton, 1974); *Cryptopone* (Clouse, 2007); *Diacamma* part (Bingham, 1903); *Echinopla* (Xu & Zhou, 2015); *Euprenolepis* (LaPolla, 2009); *Hypoponera* part (Clouse, 2007); *Iridomyrmex* (Heterick & Shattuck, 2011); *Leptogenys* (Arimoto & Yamane, 2018); *Monomorium* part (Clouse, 2007); *Myopias* (Probst et al., 2015); *Myrmecina* (Okido et al., 2020); *Myrmicaria* (Zettel et al., 2018); *Nylanderia* part (Wachkoo & Bharti, 2015); *Odontomachus* (Sorger & Zettel, 2011; Zettel & Sorger, 2023); *Odontoponera* (Yamane, 2009); *Parasyscia* (Chen et al., 2022); *Plagiolepis* (Phosrithong et al., 2024); *Plathythyrea* (Jaitrong et al., 2022); *Polyrhachis* part (Kohout, 1987; 2004; 2006; 2008; 2013; 2014; Karmaly, 2004); *Prenolepis* (Williams & LaPolla, 2018); *Pseudolasius* (Xu, 1997); *Pheidole* part (Eguchi, 2001); *Pristomyrmex* (Zettel, 2006); *Strumigenys* (Bolton, 2000; Tang & Guénard, 2023); *Tapinoma* (Seifert, 2022); *Technomyrmex* (Bolton, 2007); *Tetramorium* (Bolton, 1976; 1977; 1980); *Tetraoponera* (Ward, 2001). We also used online resources, including AntWeb (2025) and AntWiki (2025), to confirm our species identifications.

Voucher specimens were deposited at the University of California Davis Collection (UCDC), National Science Museum of Mindanao State University-Iligan Institute of Technology (MSU- IIT) and Premier Research of Institute for Science and Mathematics of MSU-IIT (PRISM).

The focus stacks, consisting of approximately 25-45 images of the new Philippine records, were captured using a Keyence VHX-970F digital microscope with a 3.19-megapixel CMOS image sensor (Keyence Corporation of America, Itasca, IL, USA) and built-in automated z-stepping.

Results

A total of 202 species representing 46 genera within seven subfamilies were collected in three sampling areas in Misamis Oriental, Mindanao, Philippines, with species listed alphabetically by subfamily in Table 1. This study significantly expanded the known insect fauna, recording six apparent new Philippine species, 17 new Mindanao records, and 19 endemic species.

Table 1. Checklist of species collected in Misamis Oriental.

TAXA	NOTES
Dolichoderinae	
<i>Dolichoderus thoracicus</i>	
<i>Iridomyrmex anceps</i>	
<i>Ochetellus glaber</i>	
<i>Tapinoma melanocephalum</i>	
<i>Tapinoma jandai</i>	new Philippine record
<i>Technomyrmex grandis</i>	
<i>Technomyrmex pratensis</i>	
<i>Technomyrmex sundaicus</i>	
Dorylinae	
<i>Aenictus gracilis</i>	
<i>Aenictus itoi_nr</i>	new Philippine record

<i>Aenictus laeviceps</i>	
<i>Lioponera</i> indet_01	
<i>Parasyscia indica</i> _nr	new Philippine record
Ectatomminae	
<i>Stictoponera binghamii</i>	
<i>Stictoponera menadensis</i>	new Mindanao record
Formicinae	
<i>Anoplolepis gracilipes</i>	
<i>Camponotus</i> indet_01	
<i>Camponotus</i> indet_02	
<i>Camponotus</i> indet_03	
<i>Camponotus</i> indet_04	
<i>Camponotus</i> indet_05	
<i>Camponotus</i> indet_06	
<i>Camponotus</i> indet_07	
<i>Camponotus</i> indet_08	
<i>Camponotus</i> indet_09	
<i>Camponotus</i> indet_10	
<i>Camponotus</i> indet_11	
<i>Camponotus</i> indet_12	
<i>Camponotus</i> indet_13	
<i>Camponotus</i> indet_14	
<i>Camponotus</i> indet_15	
<i>Camponotus</i> indet_16	
<i>Camponotus</i> indet_17	
<i>Camponotus rufifemur</i>	
<i>Camponotus stefanshoedli</i>	Endemic
<i>Colobopsis corallina</i>	Endemic
<i>Colobopsis corallina</i> _nr	
<i>Colobopsis</i> indet_01	
<i>Colobopsis leonardi</i>	
<i>Colobopsis vitrea</i>	
<i>Echinopla pallipes</i>	
<i>Echinopla striata</i>	
<i>Echinopla vermiculata</i>	
<i>Euprenolepis procera</i>	
<i>Myrmoteris williamsi</i>	Endemic; new Mindanao record
<i>Nylanderia</i> indet_01	
<i>Nylanderia</i> indet_02	
<i>Nylanderia</i> indet_02_nr	
<i>Paraparatrechina</i> indet_01	
<i>Paraparatrechina</i> indet_02	
<i>Paraparatrechina iridescens</i>	Endemic
<i>Paratrechina longicornis</i>	Introduced; invasive
<i>Polyrhachis carbonaria</i>	
<i>Polyrhachis cybele</i>	
<i>Polyrhachis aculeata</i>	new Mindanao record

<i>Polyrhachis armata</i>	
<i>Polyrhachis bicolor aurinasis</i>	
<i>Polyrhachis danum</i>	new Philippine record
<i>Polyrhachis dives</i>	
<i>Polyrhachis empesoi</i>	Endemic
<i>Polyrhachis exotica</i>	Endemic
<i>Polyrhachis fruhstorferi</i>	new Mindanao record
<i>Polyrhachis fruhstorferi_nr</i>	new Mindanao record
<i>Polyrhachis illaudata</i>	
<i>Polyrhachis</i> indet_01	
<i>Polyrhachis</i> indet_02	
<i>Polyrhachis</i> indet_03	
<i>Polyrhachis</i> indet_03_nr	
<i>Polyrhachis</i> indet_04	
<i>Polyrhachis</i> indet_05	
<i>Polyrhachis</i> indet_06	
<i>Polyrhachis</i> indet_07	
<i>Polyrhachis</i> indet_08	
<i>Polyrhachis</i> indet_09	
<i>Polyrhachis</i> indet_10	
<i>Polyrhachis</i> indet_11	
<i>Polyrhachis</i> indet_12	
<i>Polyrhachis</i> indet_13	
<i>Polyrhachis</i> indet_14	
<i>Polyrhachis</i> indet_15	
<i>Polyrhachis</i> indet_16	
<i>Polyrhachis</i> indet_17	
<i>Polyrhachis</i> indet_18	
<i>Polyrhachis</i> indet_19	
<i>Polyrhachis</i> indet_20	
<i>Polyrhachis</i> indet_21	
<i>Polyrhachis</i> indet_22	
<i>Polyrhachis</i> indet_23	
<i>Polyrhachis</i> indet_24	
<i>Polyrhachis</i> indet_25	
<i>Polyrhachis</i> indet_26	
<i>Polyrhachis</i> indet_27	
<i>Polyrhachis</i> indet_28	
<i>Polyrhachis</i> indet_29	
<i>Polyrhachis</i> indet_30	
<i>Polyrhachis</i> indet_31	
<i>Polyrhachis</i> indet_32	
<i>Polyrhachis</i> indet_33	
<i>Polyrhachis</i> indet_34	
<i>Polyrhachis</i> indet_35	
<i>Polyrhachis</i> indet_36	
<i>Polyrhachis</i> indet_37	
<i>Polyrhachis</i> indet_38	

<i>Polyrhachis indet_39</i>	
<i>Polyrhachis inermis</i>	
<i>Polyrhachis manni</i>	
<i>Polyrhachis mindanaensis</i>	Endemic
<i>Polyrhachis mucronata_nr</i>	
<i>Polyrhachis nigropilosa</i>	new Mindanao record
<i>Polyrhachis olybria</i>	
<i>Polyrhachis olybria_nr</i>	
<i>Polyrhachis pellita</i>	Endemic
<i>Polyrhachis pellita_nr</i>	The related species <i>P. pellita</i> is endemic
<i>Polyrhachis pubescens</i>	new Mindanao record
<i>Polyrhachis rastellata</i>	
<i>Polyrhachis rufipes</i>	new Mindanao record
<i>Polyrhachis saevissima</i>	
<i>Polyrhachis scabra</i>	Endemic
<i>Polyrhachis sculpturata</i>	new Mindanao record
<i>Polyrhachis semiinermis</i>	Endemic
<i>Polyrhachis vindex</i>	new Mindanao record
<i>Prenolepis jerdoni</i>	new Mindanao record
<i>Pseudolasius indet_01</i>	
Myrmicinae	
<i>Acanthomyrmex mindanao</i>	
<i>Aphaenogaster feae</i>	
<i>Cardiocondyla latifrons</i>	Endemic; new Mindanao record
<i>Crematogaster ampullaris</i>	
<i>Crematogaster arm01</i>	
<i>Crematogaster arm02</i>	
<i>Crematogaster arm02_nr</i>	
<i>Crematogaster arm03</i>	
<i>Crematogaster arm04</i>	
<i>Crematogaster arm05</i>	
<i>Crematogaster bicolor imbellis</i>	new Mindanao record
<i>Crematogaster brunnea ruginota</i>	
<i>Crematogaster onusta_nr1</i>	
<i>Crematogaster onusta_nr2</i>	
<i>Crematogaster semperi</i>	new Mindanao record
<i>Crematogaster semperi_nr</i>	new Mindanao record
<i>Carebara affinis</i>	
<i>Carebara diversa</i>	
<i>Carebara indet_01</i>	
<i>Cataulacus granulatus</i>	
<i>Monomorium floricola_nr</i>	
<i>Monomorium indet_01</i>	
<i>Myrmecina yamanei</i>	
<i>Myrmecaria aphidicola</i>	Endemic
<i>Myrmecaria arm_01</i>	
<i>Pheidole aglae</i>	

<i>Pheidole clypeocornis</i>	
<i>Pheidole hortensis</i>	
<i>Pheidole</i> indet_01	
<i>Pheidole</i> indet_02	
<i>Pheidole</i> indet_03	
<i>Pheidole</i> indet_04	
<i>Pheidole</i> indet_05	
<i>Pheidole</i> indet_06	
<i>Pheidole megacephala</i> _nr	The related species <i>P. megacephala</i> is introduced
<i>Pheidole plagiaria</i> _nr	
<i>Pheidole plinii</i>	
<i>Pheidole rabo</i>	
<i>Pheidole sayapensis</i>	
<i>Pheidole sayapensis</i> _nr	
<i>Pheidole singaporensis</i>	
<i>Plagiolepis bicolor</i>	new Philippine record
<i>Pristomyrmex hirsutus</i>	Endemic
<i>Pristomyrmex punctatus</i>	
<i>Pristomyrmex quadridens</i>	
<i>Solenopsis geminata</i>	Introduced; invasive
<i>Tetramorium</i> indet_01	
<i>Tetramorium</i> indet_02	
<i>Tetramorium</i> indet_03	
<i>Tetramorium</i> indet_04	
<i>Tetramorium</i> indet_05	
<i>Tetramorium</i> indet_06	
<i>Tetramorium pacificum</i>	
<i>Tetramorium pacificum</i> _nr	
<i>Tetramorium validiusculum</i>	new Philippine record
<i>Tetramorium wroughtonii</i>	
<i>Vollenhovia</i> indet_01	
<i>Vollenhovia</i> indet_02	
<i>Vollenhovia</i> indet_03	
<i>Vollenhovia</i> indet_04	
<i>Vollenhovia</i> indet_05	
<i>Vombisidris</i> arm01	
Ponerinae	
<i>Brachyoponera chinensis</i>	
<i>Brachyoponera obsurans</i>	
<i>Diacamma sculptum</i>	
<i>Ectomomyrmex</i> indet_01	
<i>Hypoponera confinis</i>	
<i>Hypoponera pruinosa</i>	new Mindanao record
<i>Leptogenys diminuta</i>	
<i>Myopias lobosa</i>	Endemic
<i>Odontomachus</i> indet_01	
<i>Odontomachus pangantihoni</i> _nr	the related species <i>O. pangantihoni</i> is endemic
<i>Odontomachus philippinus</i>	new Mindanao record

<i>Odontomachus scifictus</i>	Endemic
<i>Odontomachus simillimus</i>	Endemic
<i>Odontoponera denticulata</i>	
Pseudomyrmicinae	
<i>Tetraoponera allaborans</i>	
<i>Tetraoponera extenuata</i>	

Data on the new Philippine records

Subfamily Dorylinae Leach, 1815

Genus *Aenictus* Shuckard, 1840

Aenictus itoi_nr (cf. *Aenictus itoi* Jaitrong & Yamane, 2013)

New material examined

PHILIPPINES: 1w; Mindanao, Mindanao, Misamis Oriental, Balingoan, Mimbilisan Protected Landscape; 8.94361, 124.85806, 480 masl; 02 Dec 2023; lowland riparian forest, collected by sifting of leaf litter; col. A. R. Monding; ARM0789.2; MSU-IIT

Remarks

New material collected at Balingoan in the north of Mindanao was identified as *Aenictus itoi_nr* using Jaitrong & Yamane's (2013) key. This species differs from *Aenictus itoi* by its longer-than-broad head and strongly convex promesonotal dorsum, compared to the latter's subequal head and simply convex dorsum.

Distribution

Philippines; the related species, *A. itoi* occurs in Indonesia (Jaitrong & Yamane, 2013).

Figure 2. *Aenictus itoi_nr*: head in dorsal view (A), dorsal view (B), lateral view (C). CASENT4033030

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Subfamily Dorylinae Leach, 1815

Tribe Plagiolepidini, Forel 1886

Genus *Parasyscia* Emery, 1882

*Parasyscia indica*_nr (cf. *Parasyscia indica* Brown, 1975)

New material examined

PHILIPPINES: 1w; Mindanao, Misamis Oriental, Claveria, Aposkahoy, near Cabulig river; 8.69583, 125.00472, 1152 masl; 25 Apr 2024; mixed dipterocarp forest; col. A. R. Monding; ARM1241; MSU-IIT

Remarks

New material collected at Gingoog City in the north of Mindanao was identified as *Parasyscia indica*_nr using Chen et al., 2022 taxonomic key. This species is distinguished from *Parasyscia indica* lies in the occipital margin of the head, which terminates prior to the promesonotum (as opposed to extending onto it), and petiole is approximately quadrate rather than distinctly longer than wide.

Distribution

Philippines; the related species, *P. indica* occurs in India (Brown, 1975).

Figure 3. *Parasyscia indica*_nr: head in dorsal view (A), dorsal view (B), lateral view (C). CASENT4033031

Subfamily Formicinae, Latreille 1809

Tribe Plagiolepidini, Forel 1886

Genus *Plagiolepis*, Mayr 1861

Plagiolepis bicolor, Forel 1901

New material examined

PHILIPPINES: 3w; Mindanao, Misamis Oriental, Gingoog City, Gingoog hills, foot of Mt. Sumagaya-Lumot Range; 8.71694, 125.04278, 865 masl; 24 Apr 2024; mixed dipterocarp forest adjacent to banana plantation, found on a leaf of a tree; col. A. R. Monding; ARM1179; MSU-IIT

Remarks

New material collected at Gingoog City in the north of Mindanao was identified as *Plagiolepis bicolor* using Phosrithong et al., 2022 taxonomic key, the first record of the species in the Philippines.

Distribution

Singapore (Wang et al., 2022); New Guinea (Forel, 1901); Australasia; Philippines (new record)

Figure 4. *Plagiolepis bicolor*: head in dorsal view (A), dorsal view (B), lateral view (C). CASENT4033192

Subfamily Formicinae, Latreille 1809

Tribe Camponotini Forel 1878

Genus *Polyrhachis* Smith, F., 1857

Polyrhachis danum Kohout, 2006

New material examined

PHILIPPINES: 1w; Mindanao, Misamis Oriental, Claveria, Lunotan, foot of Mt. Sumagaya- Lumot Range; 8.68333, 125.00944, 1431 masl; 30 Jun 2022; secondary montane forest; col. A. R. Monding; ARM0289.1; MSU-IIT

Remarks

New material collected at Claveria in the north of Mindanao was identified as *Polyrhachis danum* using reference material and online sources Antweb.org and Antwiki.org, the first record of the species in the Philippines.

Distribution

Borneo, Indonesia, Malaysia (Kohout, 2006); Philippines (new record)

Figure 5. *Polyrhachis danum*: head in dorsal view (A), dorsal view (B), lateral view (C). CASENT4033638

Subfamily Dolichoderinae, Forel, 1878

Tribe Tapinomini, Emery, 1913

Genus *Tapinoma*, Foerster, 1850

Tapinoma jandai, Seifert, 2025

New material examined

PHILIPPINES: 1w; Mindanao, Misamis Oriental, Balingoan, Mimbilisan Protected Landscape; 8.94361, 124.85806, 480 masl; 06 Apr 2023; lowland riparian forest, collected with

Tetraoponera extenuata in a guava (*Psidium guajava*) plant; col. A. R. Monding; ARM0402; MSU-IIT • 1w; same locality and approximate coordinates as ARM0402; 3 Dec 2023; collected in the pitfall trap; col. A. R. Monding; ARM0802; MSU-IIT

Remarks

New material collected at Balingoan in the north of Mindanao was first identified as *Tapinoma pithecorum* using Seifert's (2022) taxonomic key. Later on, Seifert (2025) announced the *T. pithecorum* is the same as *T. pygmaeum* but with a rare color variation. *T. jandai* differs from *T. melanocephalum* and *T. pygmaeum* in having a smaller scape length in relation to head width. This is the first record of the species in the Philippines.

Distribution

Papua New Guinea, India (Seifert, 2025); Philippines (new record)

Figure 6. *Tapinoma jandai*: head in dorsal view (A), dorsal view (B), lateral view (C). CASENT40330

Subfamily Myrmicinae, Lepeletier de Saint-Fargeau, 1835

Tribe Crematogastrini, Forel, 1893

Genus *Tetramorium*, Mayr, 1855

Tetramorium validiusculum Emery, 1897

New material examined

PHILIPPINES: 1w; Mindanao, Misamis Oriental, Balingoan, Mimbilisan Protected Landscape; 8.94361, 124.85806, 480 masl; 01 Dec 2023; lowland riparian forest, found in a leaf; col. A. R. Monding; ARM0624; MSU-IIT • 1dq; same locality and approximate coordinates as ARM0624; 01 Dec 2023; collected in the leaf litter; col. A. R. Monding; ARM0632; MSU-IIT

Remarks

New material collected at Balingoan in the north of Mindanao was identified as *Tetramorium validiusculum* using Bolton's (1977) taxonomic key. This is the first record of the species in the Philippines. This differs from *T. cynicum* because the clypeus notch of *T. validiusculum* is not strongly pronounced.

Distribution

Australia, New Guinea, Philippines (new record)

Figure 7. *Tetramorium validiusculum*: head in dorsal view (A), dorsal view (B), lateral view (C). CASENT4033373

Presented in Table 2 are 15 species newly recorded from Mindanao, with information on their previously known island occurrences. Those that are regarded as near (“nr”) to species were not included in the table.

Table 2. List of new distributional records for Mindanao with information of their previously known Philippine distribution.

TAXA	Distribution	References
<i>Cardiocondyla latifrons</i> Seifert, 2022	Leyte	Seifert, 2022
<i>Crematogaster bicolor imbellis</i> Emery, 1893	Luzon	General & Alpert, 2012
<i>Crematogaster semperi</i> Emery, 1893	Luzon	General & Alpert, 2012
<i>Hypoponera pruinosa</i> Emery, 1900	Luzon	General & Alpert, 2012
<i>Myrmoteras williamsi</i> Wheeler, 1919	Luzon & Negros	General & Alpert, 2012
<i>Odontomachus philippinus</i> Emery, 1893	Negros, Panay, Siquijor	Sorger & Zettel, 2011 General & Alpert, 2012
<i>Prenolepis jerdoni</i> Emery, 1893	Luzon	General et al., 2020
<i>Polyrhachis aculeata</i> Mayr, 1879	Negros	General & Alpert, 2012
<i>Polyrhachis fruhstorferi</i> Emery, 1898	Only literature records	Chapman & Capco, 1951 General & Alpert, 2012
<i>Polyrhachis nigropilosa</i> Mayr, 1872	Negros & Palawan	General & Alpert, 2012
<i>Polyrhachis pubescens</i> Mayr, 1879	Luzon	General & Alpert, 2012
<i>Polyrhachis rufipes</i> F. Smith, 1858	Luzon	General & Alpert, 2012
<i>Polyrhachis sculpturata</i> F. Smith, 1860	Luzon & Palawan	General & Alpert, 2012
<i>Polyrhachis vindex</i> F. Smith, 1857	Luzon & Negros	General & Alpert, 2012
<i>Stictoponera menadensis</i> Mayr, 1887	Luzon & Negros	General & Alpert, 2012 Antwiki.org

Discussion

These new ant records for Mindanao show that the island merits continued exploration. Current data, as shown in table 2, predominantly features species previously known from Luzon, Palawan, and Negros. This uneven representation stems from a historical concentration of research efforts on those islands, with Negros being particularly well-studied, largely due to the work of Chapman.

The results show a remarkably high diversity in just one province of Mindanao. It is also apparent that there are probably new species in this collection. The significant number of new ant records discovered in Mindanao underscores the island's need for increased research. Furthermore, the lack of publicly available data from other researchers contributes to the incomplete picture of ant distribution in the Philippines.

Given our current understanding of ants in Mindanao, there is likely much more to uncover. As such, further research is crucial and urgent, especially with the ongoing economic development in some mountainous areas. Rapid economic development in mountainous regions threatens undiscovered ant species and other potentially beneficial fauna with local extinction before they can be studied.

Additionally, there is also a need for more researchers focused on accurately classifying species and understanding their relationships to enhance conservation efforts.

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